

Bridging the Gap: Staff Awareness and Utilization of Social Work Professionals in Government Teaching Hospital in Obio/Akpor LGA, Rivers State

Mina Margaret Ogbanga PhD

Rivers State University

Mina.Ogbanga@ust.edu.ng

Ndukwe Elisha Nnanna

University of Port Harcourt

Abstract

This study investigated the level of staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital; a case study of government teaching hospitals in Obia/Akpor Local Government area, Rivers State. The objective of the paper is to identify staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital. Primary source of data was generated through self-administered questionnaires. The population of the study was 800 medical staffs, while the sample size of 267 was determined using the Taro Yamane's formula for sample size determination. The study involved different cadres of hospital staff including; clinicians, nurses, radiologists, dental officers and hospital nutritionist. The result show that all the items indicate that the staffs are aware of the presences of social workers in the hospital. This is true since the mean values are above the benchmark of 2.5, meaning that most of the respondents were on the agree range of the scale. But the first item on the table 'We have sufficient number of social works to handle our patients in the hospital' ($M=1.97$; $SD=1.35538$) shows an indication that there insufficient number of social workers in the hospital. Thus it is clear that medical staffs are aware of the presents of social workers in the hospital, are aware that the social work is a department of its own, knows the location of social work. It was recommended among others that the Government should employ more hospital social workers so that they can be able to meet the demand of their services to patients and clients at the hospital.

Introduction

This chapter is an introductory part of the research study in which the research problem is introduced and its background laid down. The problem statement is provided which shows the nature of the problem. Furthermore, the chapter states general and specific objectives, which have guided the study. Also explained in the chapter is the significance of the study, which shows the motivation and justifies the need and importance of conducting this research study. The evolution of Social work and efforts to promote social development can be seen as closely linked to the primordial tendency of humans to help one another in all past human societies. In traditional, including African societies, the concern for social welfare was reflected in activities within the family, the clan and ethnic group. The urge of man to help man in all societies was demonstrated by the great care accorded to, inter alia, children, orphans, widows, widowers and the invalid as well as the elderly. In such “*gemeinschaft*” (often translated as society or civil society or 'association') (Tonnies, 2001), social work was more or less a task for everyone instead of individuals and specialized agencies. As such, Social work has always been geared towards improving the quality of life of each and every one. Social work as it is known today has relatively recent origins. It emerged at a time when feudalism was disintegrating and capitalism taking its place. The control of the family and the church was fast weakening too. According to Fink (1968) cited in Friedrich (2019), these fundamental social changes began occurring between 1834 and 1909 and ushered in the development in Britain of specialized care agencies for certain vulnerable and disadvantaged groups, such as dependent children and people living with physical or mental disabilities. Institutions such as district schools, foster homes, hospitals, infirmaries and special schools were provided for these groups. At any rate, social work is increasingly becoming globalized, for it is being applied in a variety of settings and numerous agencies and people across the world are benefiting from its services. Among the social work services provided are: “psychiatry, medical, marriage and family counseling; the school; rehabilitation; corrections; public welfare; workplace; drug abuse; and child welfare” (Farley et al, 2006). Social work does not only address needs and problems at the personal or family level but also at the neighborhood, national and international level.

History has it that social work in Nigeria predates colonialism. Kinship system in the traditional Nigerian society provided for family welfare, child welfare, health, mental health, care for the aged, informal education, social planning and development. Extended family met

social welfare needs and dealt with problematic behaviours that the community regarded as deviant. However, a well-packaged, formal social work as a profession with well-articulated theories began with colonization in Nigeria (Anucha, 2008). Lagos had for long been in the fore-front of the development of social work in Nigeria significantly during World War II returnees and its attendant social welfare-related problems. The Institute of Social work had been growing and expanding. Currently Nigerian Association of Social Worker (NASOW), Department of Social work (DSW) and Institute of Social work (ISW) are working on establishment of social work council in Nigeria; a bill is on the process for establishing a council of social work for regulating social work practice and education which will spearhead social work profession to a great extent. Samadi, R. (2008); highlighted history of social work in health care system that social workers from the twentieth century have been involved in health care system such as providing services for poor people, worked with the elderly and patients with tuberculosis. In 1977, the World Association of Social Work published standards for the provision of health care services in hospitals and in 1980, the standards for social workers in health centers developed and it replaced hospital standards. Between 1981 and 1982, the National Association of Social Work Board's new developed standards approved and added to the previous standard of care. These standards include the activities of social workers in the field of kidney patient, disability, treatment and health care and followed by integration of social workers into the health care system and the public and private sectors were engaged. More activities of social workers concentrate on transferring the patient or refer him or her to home and in some cases solve the financial problems. In the capital of Iran, Tehran, in 1960 at Roozbeh Hospital, social work began to work, after a decade in office the of Health and Welfare and then in the Ministry of Health, Social Work Department was established.

Research Aim and Objective

- (i) Identify staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital

Research Question

- (i) What is the level of staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital?

Scope of the Study

For the sake of time and limited resources this paper seeks to investigate the challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical institutions in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study will primarily focus on the health care delivery of medical social welfare department of University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH), as this is part of the Government Teaching Hospital in Obio-Akpor LGA with a functional social work department. Also, the researcher seeks to understand the level of awareness of social work services among health workers.

Significance of the Study

The study aimed at identifying challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical cadre. The identified challenges shall be communicated to the Ministry of Social Welfare and Rehabilitation Centre and the heads of department to make them understand the existing challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical practice. The results of this research study can help in developing strategies on how to eliminate those challenges hence maximize the benefits to clients who require social workers interventions. This study will assist to create awareness to the local government authority on the need to strengthen the social welfare department in terms of allocating adequate funds as well as increasing the number of social workers into medical practice. Moreover, on job programs might be designed to orient all staff on the roles and functions of social workers into medical practice including cases required to be attended by social workers.

Limitations

The research only focused on Government Teaching Hospitals in Obia/Akpor LGA in Rivers State. Hence, the findings may not be adequate in generalizing it to cover other medical institutions. The second factor is that there is a wide geographical scope of Hospitals in Rivers State which was difficult to visit all which may affect conclusion and generalization of findings.

Another major limitation is that the respondent of this study are medical workers who have little or no time for activities outside their working schedule. Hence, the retrieval of questionnaire was greatly as only 215 out of 267 questionnaires that were distributed were retrieved.

Definition of Terms

Social Worker

Within the United States, a social worker is an individual who possesses a baccalaureate or master's degree in social work from a school or program accredited by the Council on Social Work Education. Although all 50 states and the District of Columbia license or certify social workers, licensure and certification laws vary by state. Each social worker should be licensed or certified, as applicable and required, at the level appropriate to her or his scope of practice in the practitioner's jurisdiction(s).

Meaning and definition of social work

Social work is a broad profession that intersects with several disciplines. Social work organizations offer the following definitions:

“Social work is a practice-based profession and an academic discipline that promotes social change and development, social cohesion, and the empowerment and liberation of people. Principles of social justice, human rights, collective responsibility and respect for diversities are central to social work. Underpinned by theories of social work, social sciences, humanities and indigenous knowledge, social work engages people and structures to address life challenges and enhance well-being.” –International Federation of Social Workers (IFSW 2014)

Major Issues and Constraints on Social Work: An African Perspective

Compared to other helping professions like medicine, psychiatry and nursing, social work is a relatively young profession. In Europe and North America, social work emerged in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century. In Africa social work is even younger, essentially a product of European colonialism. Despite its recent development, social work is a rapidly growing field. The profession's phenomenal growth and development throughout the world is a clear indication of its contribution to the alleviation of social problems. However, social work is still a fledgling and struggling profession, whose theory and practice are shrouded in mystery and controversy. Indeed, a number of scholars have described social work as a

profession of many faces: stimulating, challenging, confusing and even frustrating, The enigma and controversy surrounding social work is partly rooted in its newness and also in the wide array of the concepts, theories, principles, methods and techniques which social workers use. Accordingly, the major issues and problems facing social work today revolve around its structure, functions, identity, resources and education. (Midgley, 2007; Macpherson & Midgley, 2008). Romile and Raditlhokwa (2006) in a journal article, said; a major problem which social workers have to deal with is the vagueness and controversy surrounding the meaning, objectives, functions and methods of their profession. Social work as a field of study and practice is not well understood, especially in Africa. This is largely due to the fact that social work is a profession still in its infancy. Below an attempt is made to define and explain the characteristics, origins and functions of social work.

Research Method

The Study Area

The study was conducted at University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) Port Harcourt. The area is selected as one of the government hospitals with social work professionals working with other medical field practitioners.

Research Design

Nachimias (2003) defined research design as "the blue print that enables the investigators to come up with solutions to problems and guide him/her in the various stages of the research. This study adopts a descriptive cross sectional survey. Cross-sectional surveys are studies aimed at determining the frequency or level of a particular attribute in a defined population at a particular point in time. A cross sectional study is commonly used in medical and social science researches. A cross sectional study or prevalence study is the type of observational study that involves the analysis of data collected from a population or representative subset at one specific point in time. The data were collected using questionnaires which were given to respondents and the analysis of the collected data portrayed the factors that challenge integration of social work professionals in medical services.

Population of the Study

According to Nachimias (2003) population is defined as “the aggregate of all cases that conform to some designated set of specification. Kombo and Tromp (2006) defined population as the largest group from which the sample is taken. The population of the study comprises all the medical staffs of the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital working with social welfare department in the hospital which is about 800 in number. This number was obtained from the human resource department of the hospital.

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Nachimias (2003) defined sample as “the sub set of a population”. Thus, in view of the fact that our study involves a finite population, a sample size that can be possibly reached is obtained. Kothari (2004) defined sampling techniques or procedure as “a definite plan for obtaining a sample for population given. The study sample size was arrived at using the Taro Yamen’s 1970 formula.

The sample size was calculated by using the Taro Yamen Sample size determination formula;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Whereby; n=Sample size, N= total population (800) and e= an acceptable error (0.05).

$$\text{Therefore } n = \frac{800}{1+800(0.05)^2} = 266.7$$

In this research study the sample size was 267.

Data Collection Method

Questionnaire

The questionnaire involves a set of questions to collect information from subjects on their perceptions, feelings to the subject under study. It helps in providing accurate data that are quantifiable easily. The study which is dominantly quantitative in nature, adopts the structured questionnaire in the generation of primary data for the study. Copies of questionnaire would be personally administered, followed up and retrieved.

Data Analysis Approach

Braun and Clarke (2006) state that “thematic analysis is a qualitative analytic method for identifying, analyzing and reporting patterns within data. Thematic analysis minimally organizes and described data set in details. However, it goes further than this and interprets various aspect of the research topic. Data collected from the field were structured to ensure consistency of responses. Data generated were arranged and coded according to themes and then fed into the data editor section of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 21.0). Analysis were undertaken in two phases beginning with the demographic profile, using percentages, describes the frequencies of responses to various sample characteristics. Secondly the research questions and findings were analyzed through mean scores and standard deviations

Validity of the Instrument

According to Babbie (2007), the term validity refers to the extent to which an empirical measure adequately reflects the real meaning of the concept under consideration. Validity is defined as the ability of the scale to measure what it is designed or purported to measure. For validity of the measurement to be established, there should be a complete absence of measurement error. It is important that a reliability and validity test be carried out comprehensively at every stage of the research work. Babbie (2007) posit that, after operationalizing, defining variables and applying different scaling techniques, it is pertinent to ensure that each research instrument employed be adequately tested for reliability and validity. In this study, the researcher ensured that the measure for reliability included an adequate and effective representative set of items that tap the concept. Serious effort was made to ensure that the scale items represented the domain or universe of the concept being measured. In other words, the measurement is a function of how well the dimensions and indicators of the various concepts are been delineated, which logically reflected the study variables. The validation of the instrument would be ensured through my supervisors vetting. Through this process, errors in the questionnaire such as ambiguity, contradictory questions, poor wording of questions, misleading or poor instructions among others would be detected and eliminated.

Tests of Reliability of Instrument

Reliability is the ability of a measuring instrument to achieve consistent results each time it is adopted. However, Nunnally (1979) asserts that the reliability alpha values in determining the internal consistency of the instrument should maintain a minimum threshold of 0.7. Based on this, the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient method was utilized in this study since it is the most predominant method of testing reliability in social sciences research (Hair, Black, Babin & Anderson 2010).

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Presentation of Data

Table 1; Administration and Retrieval of Questionnaire

	Number of Cases	Percentage
Copies of Questionnaire Administered	267	100
Copies of Questionnaire Retrieved/Returned	215	80.5
Copies of Questionnaire not returned	52	19.5
Uncompleted/unusable Copies of Questionnaire	10	3.7
Completed and Usable Copies of Questionnaire	205	76.8

Source: Research Survey Data, 2019

From Table 1, it is observed that 267 questionnaire were administered to respondents. 215 copies of questionnaire representing 80.5 percent were returned. However, 52 copies of questionnaire representing 19.5 percent were not returned. 10 copies of questionnaire representing 3.7 percent were not correctly filled and thus unsuitable for data analysis while 205 copies of questionnaire representing 76.8 percent were correctly filled and thus suitable for data analysis.

2. Demographic Analysis

In this study the output of the demographic analysis were presented. These presentations would further enable the understanding of demographic distribution of the sample.

Table 2 Gender Distribution of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Female	120	58.5	58.5	58.5
Valid Male	85	41.5	41.5	100.0
Total	205	100.0	100.0	

Source: Research Survey Data, 2019

Figure 4.1: bar chart showing sex distribution of respondents

Table 2 shows that 118 (57.6%) of the respondents are females while 87 representing (42.4%) of the respondents are male. Implying that our respondents are largely female- dominated.

Analysis of Research Question

Research Questions One:

What is the level of staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital?

Table 3: Response Rates on the staff awareness of the presence of social work professionals in the hospital.

	Staff awareness on the presence of social	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Std.
1	I am aware of the presence of social workers in the hospital	67	103	8	8	19	3.93	1.16536
2	I am aware of the location of social work unit in the hospital	53	120	8	12	12	3.93	1.02876
3	Social work is a department of its own in the hospital	56	120	5	15	9	3.97	0.99465
4	Social workers are part of the medical team	74	104	9	6	12	4.08	1.02324
5	We have sufficient number of social workers to handle our patients in the hospital	18	20	16	34	117	1.97	1.35538

Source: Research Survey Data, 2019

The result of table 3 reveals that all items (1-5) have mean scores above 3.50, except the last item which has the mean score of 1.97. The statement ‘Social workers are part of the medical team’ has the highest mean score (M=4.08; SD=1.02324) followed by ‘social work is a department of its own in the hospital’ (M=3.97; SD= 0.99465), ‘I am aware of the location of the social work unit in the hospital’ (M=3.93;SD=1.02876), ‘I am aware of the presences of social workers in the hospital’ (M=3.93;SD=1.16536). These show that all the items indicate that the staffs are aware of the presences of social workers in the hospital. This is true since the mean values are above the benchmark of 2.5, meaning that most of the respondents were on the agree range of the scale. But the first item on the table ‘We have sufficient number of social works to handle our patients in the hospital’ (M=1.97; SD=1.35538) shows an indication that there insufficient number of social workers in the hospital. Thus it is clear that medical staffs are aware of the presents of social workers in the hospital, are aware that the social work is a department of its own, knows the location of social work unit in the hospital, and are also aware that they are part of the medical team in the hospital.

Summary and Conclusion

The study used a cross sectional survey research design. The target population comprised 800 medical staff of government hospitals in Obia/Akpor LGA of Rivers State. The sample size was obtained using Taro Yamane sample size determination formula. The study sample was 267. The content validity of the instrument was achieved using supervisor's vetting and approval while the internal consistency of instrument was achieved using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient with all the items being above 0.70. Generally, the findings of this research study have shown that; the idea of incorporating social work department into medical services is positively accepted and appreciated by a wide range of health care staff. The study results indicate that the majority of hospital medical staff (82.9%) indicated to be aware on the presence of social workers at the hospital; however few medical staff (17.1%) are unable to identify the presence of social workers at the hospital.

Recommendations

The elimination of the challenges relating to integration of social work professionals into medical service; requires use of multidisciplinary action by involving a cross section of government officials from higher to lower management level. The professional body and social workers should be part and parcel to make valuable and sound contributions to find ways to overcome these challenges. The recommendations from the researcher will not differ very much from those of the respondents. These recommendations are directed to the Ministry of Labour and Employment, Ministry of Health, Community Development, Gender, Elders and Children, Regional, Secretaries District Executive directors, Regional Medical Officers, District Medical Officers, National Association of Social Workers and Hospital Social Workers. Based on the discussion and conclusion above, the following recommendations are hereby made:

- i. The Government should employ more hospital social workers so that they can be able to meet the demand of their services to patients and clients at the hospital.
- ii. Social workers should be made known to all hospital staff and their roles should be well communicated.

Reference

- Ankrah, E. M. (2001). "Social Work Uganda: Survival in the Midst of Turbulence," in Hokenstad, M.; Khinduka, S. & Midgley, J. Profiles in International Social Work, Washington, DC: NASW Press.
- Anucha, U., (2008). Exploring a New Direction for Social Work Education and Training in Nigeria. *Social Work Education*. 27. 229-242. 10.1080/02615470701381459.
- Babbie, E. (2007) *The practice of social research*. 11th Edition, Thompson Wadsworth, Belmont.
- Bar-On, A. A. (2004). "The Elusive Boundaries of Social Work," *Journal of Sociology and Social Welfare*, 21(3), 53-67.
- Barker, M. (2013), Anaesthetic emergencies. *Veterinary Nursing Journal*, 28: 220-224. doi:10.1111/vnj.12047
- Barr, M. S. (2004). *Banking the poor: Policies to bring low-income Americans into the financial mainstream*. Washington, D.C.: Brookings Institution.
- Blyton, P. & Turnbull, P. (1992), 'HRM: Debates, Dilemmas and Contradictions', in P. Blyton & P. Turnbull (eds), *Reassessing Human Resource Management*, London: Sage, Publications Inc.
- Birkenmaier, J., & Curley, J., (2009). "Financial credit: Social work's role in empowering low-income families". *Journal of Community Practice*. 17(3):251–268.
- Braun, V., and Clarke, V. (2006). *Using the thematic analysis in psychology*. *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2), 77-101. London: Routledge.
- Breakwell, G. M. & Rowell, C. (2002). *Social Work: The Social Psychological Approach*, Berkshire: Van Nostrand Reinhold Co.
- Breakwell, G. M. & Rowell, C. (2002). *Social Work: The Social Psychological Approach*, Berkshire: Van Nostrand Reinhold Co.
- Breakwell, G. M., & Rowett, C. (1982). *Social Work: The Social Psychological Approach*. Wokingham, U. K.: Van Nostrand Reinhold.

Canadian Association of Social Workers "What is Social Work?" www.casw-acts.ca. Retrieved May 13, 2019.

Canadian Association of Social Workers "What is Social Work?" www.casw-acts.ca. Retrieved July 17, 2019.

Canadian Association of Social Workers "What is Social Work?" www.casw-acts.ca. Retrieved July 19, 2019.

Child, J. (1969). *British Management Thought: A Critical Analysis*, London: George Allen & Unwin.

[Charity Organization Societies: 1877-1893 - Social Welfare History Project](#)". *Social Welfare History Project*. February 4, 2013. Retrieved December 29, 2017.

Crisp, B.R., & Beddoe, L., (2012). *Promoting Health and Well-being in Social Work Education*. Routledge.

Despard, M., & Chowa, G.A.N., (2010). "Social workers' interest in building individuals' financial capabilities". *Journal of Financial Therapy*. 1 (1): 23–41.

Digestive Program". *Current Problems in Pediatric and Adolescent Health Care*. 48 (4): 111–112.

[Dorrien, G., \(2011\). "Fostering Democratic Citizenship: Jane Addams". *Social Ethics in the Making: Interpreting an American Tradition*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons. p. 168. ISBN 9781444393798](#). Retrieved May 13, 2019.

Dunlop, J. T. (1958) *Industrial Relations Systems*. New York: Holt Rinehart and Winston
Fajana, S. (2000) *Industrial Relations in Nigeria: Theory and Features* (2nd Ed.). Lagos: Labofinpublishers

Eysenck, H. J. Charles C. T., (1967). *The biological basis of personality*. Springfield, IL:

Ferdinand Tönnies (ed. Jose Harris), *Community and Civil Society*, Cambridge University Press (2001), hardcover, 266 pages, ISBN 0-521-56119-1; trade paperback, Cambridge University Press (2001), 266 pages, ISBN 0-521-56782-3

Flexner, A., (2018). "Is social work a profession?". New York, The New York school of philanthropy – via Internet Archive.

Fonash, A., (2018). "The Role of the Medical Social Worker in a Pediatric Aero-

Francis J. T., (2005). [Encyclopedia of Canadian Social Work](#). Wilfrid Laurier Univ. Press. pp. 219, 236. [ISBN 978-0-88920-436-2](#).

Fink, C. F. (1968). Some conceptual difficulties in the theory of social conflict. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 12(4), 412–460.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/002200276801200402>

Fubara, B.A. and Mguni, B.S (2005) *Research Methods in Management* Port Harcourt, Pear Publishers Pp 50-92.

["Global Definition of Social Work | International Federation of Social Workers".ifsw.org](#). Retrieved July 19, 2017

Grinker, R. R., MacGregor, H., Selan, K., Klein, A., & Kohrman, J., (1961). *Early years of psychiatric social work*. *Social Service Review*, 35, 111–126.

Guest, D. (1989). Human Resource Management: Its Implications for Industrial Relations and Trade Unions', in J. Storey (ed.), *New Perspectives on Human Resource Management*,

Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis*. (7th ed.). Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.

Huff, D., (1900) "[Chapter I. Scientific Philanthropy](#)". *The Social Work History Station*. [Boise State University](#). Retrieved February 20, 2008.

International Federation of Social Workers [Global Definition of Social Work](#) ifsw.org. Retrieved May 13, 2019.

Jarrett, M. C. (1918): Psychiatric social work. In: *Mental Hygiene* 2, pp. 283-290.

Keough, M. E; Samuels, M. F., (2004). "The Kosovo Family Support Project: Offering Psychosocial Support for Families with Missing Persons". *Social Work*. 49 (4): 587–594. doi:10.1093/sw/49.4.587.

- Khinduka, S. K. (2001). "Social working the Third World," in *Social Services Review*, 45(4), 62- 72.
- Kirt, J., and Miller, M. L. (1986). *Reliability and Validity in Qualitative Research*. Beverly Hills: Sage Publications Inc.
- Kombo, D. K. and Tromp D. L. A., (2006). *Proposal and Thesis Writing: An introduction*. Nairobi: Pauline's publications Africa.
- Kothari, C.R. (2004) *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques*. 2nd Edition, New Age International Publishers, New Delhi.
- Macpherson, S, (1982). *Social Policy in the Third World: The Social Dilemmas of Underdevelopment*, Brighton: Wheatsheaf Books.
- Macpherson, S., &Midgley, J, (2008). *Comparative Social Policy and the Third World*, Brighton: Wheatsheaf Books.
- Maslow, A. H. (1954). *Motivation and personality*. New York: Harper and Row.
- Mayo, E. (1933). *The Human Problems of Industrial Civilization*, New York: Macmillan Company.
- Morris, P. (2008). Reinterpreting Abraham Flexner's Speech, "Is Social Work a Profession?": Its Meaning and Influence on the Field's Early Professional Development. *Social Service Review*, 82(1), 29-60. doi:10.1086/529399
- Murali D. N; Erick G. G., (2014). *Evidence Based Macro Practice in Social Work*. Gregory Publishing Company. ISBN 978-0-911541-94-6.
- Midgley, J. (1981). *Professional Imperialism: Social work the Third World*, London: Heinemann.
- Nachimias, J. (2003). *Research methodology in the Social Science*.(5th Ed): London: St. Mart Press Inc.
- .

Nair, U., Yen, W. L., Mari, M., Cao, Y., Xie, Z., Baba, M., ...Klionsky, D. J. (2012). A role for Atg8-PE deconjugation in autophagosome biogenesis. *Autophagy*, 8(5), 780–793. doi:10.4161/auto.19385

National Association of Social Workers "Code of Ethics (English and Spanish)" socialworkers.org. Archived from the original on June 6, 2002.

National Association of Social Workers (NASW), www.naswdc.org. Archived from [the original](#) on May 31, 2002. Retrieved July 19, 2019.

"National Association of Social Workers".NASW.Retrieved September 6, 2019.

Nunnally, J. C. (1978). *Psychometric theory* (2nd ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill "Ontario College of Social Workers and Social Service Workers: The Centre for Education & Training" (PDF). 2011. Retrieved November 8, 2019

PhyllidaParsole. Risk assessment in social care and social work. 2001. Jessica Kingsley Publishers.

Popple, P. R. and Leighninger, L.,(2011) *Social Work, Social Welfare*, American Society. Boston: Allyn& Bacon

Pavesi. M, Devlin N., Hakimi Z., Nazir J., Herdman M., Hoyle C.&Odeyemi I. A. (2013) Understanding the effects on HR-QoL of treatment for overactive bladder: a detailed analysis of EQ-5D clinical trial data for mirabegron, *Journal of Medical Economics*, 16:7, 866-876, DOI: 10.3111/13696998.2013.802240

Reyna VF, Farley F (2006) Risk and Rationality in Adolescent Decision Making: Implications for Theory, Practice, and Public Policy. Administrative Affairs and Employment, (1995).Law and employment regulations. Tehran: Administrative Affairs and Employment organization publication. *Journal of Social Science for Policy Implications*, 2(2), 59 – 68.

Rex A. S., (1995). *Social Work Administration: Dynamic Management and Human Relationships*. Allyn and Bacon. pp. 2–3. ISBN 978-0-13-669037-5.

Romich, J.; Simmelink, J.; Holt, S. D., (2007). "When working harder does not pay: Low-income working families, tax liabilities, and benefit reductions" (PDF). *Families in Society*. 88 (3): 418–426. doi:10.1606/1044-3894.3651.

Rwomile, A. and Ratithokwa, L. (2006). Social work Africa: Issues and challenges. *Journal of Social Development in Africa* (1996), 11(2), 5-19.

Samadi Rad, Anvar. (2008). social work in Iran.Kayhan. *Journal of Social Science for Policy Implications*, 2(2), 59 - 68

Standards for Clinical Social Work Practice (2005). Retrieved on 16th November, 2016 from: https://www.socialworkers.org/practice/NASWClinicalSWS_tandards.pdf

Sherraden, M.; Laux, S. & Kaufman, C., (2007)."Financial education for social workers".*Journal of Community Practice*. 15 (3): 9–36. doi:10.1300/J125v15n03_02.

[Social Work Profession](#).*Encyclopedia of Social Work*.**20**. Summer 2017

NASW, Code of Ethics

Stefaroi, P., (2014). *Humane & Spiritual Qualities of the Professional in Humanistic Social Work: Humanistic Social Work – The Third Way in Theory and Practice*. Charleston: Createspace.

Stone, R. (1995). *Human Resource Management*, (2nd Edition)., Milton: Wiley & Son.

Taylor, F. (1974). *Scientific Management*, New York: Harper & Row.

Thackeray, M. G., Farley, O. W., & Skidmore, R. A. (1994). *Introduction to Social Work*, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs.

Tonnies, F. (1887). *Fundamental Concept of Sociology*, New York: Oxford University Press.

Wilson, K., Ruch, G., Lymbery, M., & Cooper, A. (2008).*Social Work*.Harlow, UK, Longman, Pearson NASW Press.

Wodarski, J. S., Feit, M. D., (2012). "Social Group Work Practice: An Evidence- Based Approach". *Journal of Evidence-Based Social Work*. 9 (4): 414–420. doi:10.1080/15433714.2012.695719. ISSN 1543-3714.

"1800s". *Family Action: About Us*. Archived from [the original](#) on July 18, 2011. Retrieved November 17, 2018.

Samadi, R. (2008) Stellar structure and evolution (488),(2), pp705 – 714

Steve, M., (2011. ")," , Asian Economic and Social Society, 1(5), 181-187.

William, M.M., Daniel, R. Z., Stephen M.J., Searle, E., 2014, *Nucleic Acids Research*, Volume 42, Issue D1, 1 January 2014, Pages D749–D755,

Yin, R. K. (1994). *Discovering the Future of the Case Study Method in Evaluation Research*. *Evaluation Practice*, 15(3), 283–290.